

ART STUDIES

AUTHOR'S ANGEL IN CINEMATOGRAPHY (BASED ON THE FILMS OF BELA TARR)

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Abstract

The article examines the authorial and camera angles in the films of director Bela Tarr. An analysis of Bela Tarr's filmography in terms of perspective allows us to conclude that the author's perspective is built precisely in relation to the window in the films. The window is the main means of expression of the author's perspective in Bela Tarr's full-length feature films. In the first stage of his work, the perspective of looking in through the window is dominant, and in the second stage, the perspective of looking out through the window is dominant.

Keywords: Bela Tarr, author's angle, camera angle, point of view, cinema.

Introduction: The importance of camera angle in cinematography stems from the fundamental function that visual elements play in shaping the language of cinema. Elements of cinematic language based on visual perception, such as montage, shot, and angle, are tools that distinguish cinematography from storytelling and reveal the "emotional consciousness of the camera". [Фельдман, 1959]. However, in cinema, there is not only the camera angle, but also the author's angle. The author's angle does not follow the camera, he observes what is happening from a single point of view. This perspective point of view, which has a static state like an immovable block whose axis does not change when lifted, and is sometimes identified with the character's point of view, determines where the author stands and from what angle he views the events. From this perspective, the double angle in cinematography - the participation of both the camera and the author's angle - leads to a double coding of the cinematic narrative.

Main part: Looking at a subject from a variety of perspectives opens up the subject's potential possibilities. Bela Tarr's filmography also presents to an audience a view of the same event from different heights - different levels of perspective on a single subject.

If we symbolically liken a director's work to the structure of a building, the perspective provided from different floors also becomes a factor that determines the director's angle. Bela Tarr's filmography reveals not only the content of the subject, but also the anatomy of the perspective from which the content is viewed, the duration of viewing, and the change that this duration creates. From this perspective, the director's full-length feature film creation can be divided into two stages: the initial stage, in which he drew towards documentary and social realism and highlighted social and socio-moral problems ("Family Nest", "The Outsider", "The Prefab People", "Almanac of Fall") and the second and final stage, where the visual elements of the cinematic language are at the forefront - the presentation of minimum communication and maximum image ("Damnation", "Satantango", "Werckmeister Harmonies", "The Man from London", "The Turin Horse"). The difference between these two stages is characterized not only by the difference in filming method and authorial style, but also by the change in the author's angle.

Bela Tarr's first film, "Family Nest" reveals the socio-moral erosions against the backdrop of the breakup of a young family facing housing problems. The author poses the question of whether social problems stem from moral flaws, or whether moral flaws stem from social problems, against the backdrop of the contrasting events and social difficulties of his time, and invites the audience to think about the difficulties and advantages of new ways of living. Using the reportage method to convey maximum reality, the director works with close-ups, highlighting the character's monologues addressed directly to the camera. The director's first full-length film, "Family Nest" can be characterized as a place closer to the ground - the basement - in his filmography, which we symbolically describe as a multi-story building, and which is still a place of controversy. The same theme - the impact of social difficulties on the breakdown of families - is continued in the film "The Prefab People": individuals deprived of emotional intelligence caused by social problems are in search of new forms of living. Having characters talk about their problems directly to the camera turns the viewer into a participant - a party to the dialogue - by setting the camera angle directly opposite the character - at eye level. Eye contact and hearing social, moral, and ethical issues directly from the character's perspective is the first step towards understanding individuals.

In "The Outsider," the social conflict from the previous films transitions into personal conflict with subtle details. Andras, a musician who abandoned his newborn baby and wife, has to change jobs frequently due to his behavior. An unstable social environment and an unbalanced psychological state reveal that his conflict is an internal one. The lack of family ties - the feeling of alienation from his brother, his own family - leads to him becoming an outsider - a constant outsider.

Although Tarr departs from the style of documentary realism with the film "Almanac of Fall", the close-ups and dialogues suggest that existence and living in life are possible only through mutual dialogues and understandings. The housemate, her son, and three other residents try out a variety of ways to live together, and what happens "behind closed doors" in various rooms of the apartment is depicted with maximum naturalism.

Bela Tarr's work in the first phase is in search of new forms of human existence at each new stage, despite social despair and impasse. In these films, the author's angle focuses on the interior of the house - what is between the four walls. Focusing the camera directly on the character's face and following the characters' facial expressions and gestures allows the problem to become concrete and materialized. The phrase "in close-up, the human face acts as a document" [Балаш, 1935] confirms the camera's documenting function. When the goal is to get to the ontological essence of the problem, the camera angle changes - instead of facing the characters, the camera starts following them, following them closely. At this point, the camera moves from passive observation to moving shoulder to shoulder with the characters like a living organism. This time, the author's angle focuses not on the inside of the house, but on the outside - on the views seen through the windows.

Bela Tarr's windows

With the film "Damnation", Bela Tarr began his collaboration with Hungarian writer Laszlo Krasznahorkai. At the same time, the films he made with composer Mihaly Vig and the director's wife, editor and director Agnes Hranitzky, constitute the second and cult stage of Bela Tarr's filmmaking. As a result of this collaboration, the writer, composer and editor rise to the level of film authors, and works emerge that organically incorporate the unity of literature, music, and cinematography.

The first frame of "Damnation" which laid the foundation for a new phase in Bela Tarr's work and defined the director's authorial angle, opens with a view of cable cars through a window. The main character, Karrer's suppressed courage, desires, and the pressure of his dreams become factors that determine his depressive behavior. This depressive and melancholic state is further enhanced by the static nature of the camera and the use of long, slow shots. In fact, minimizing the speed of events creates the effect that nothing is actually happening on the screen. The character's "immobility" contrasts with the dance scene in the bar, and through parallel montage, the emptying of the dance floor, the betrayal of the woman he loves - the only person he trusts, breaks his last drop of faith in himself and people, and causes him to completely distance himself from society. Karrer's report to official administration to "restore justice" by exposing his own plan also visualizes the character's moral surrender.

This act of surrender is continued in the director's next film, "Satantango": It's as if two reports and applications are being reviewed in two apartment on top of each other. The return of Irimiash and Petrina, suspected of fraud and deceit and rumored to be dead, to the village creates a revival among the villagers. The farm residents, who plan to build a new life by taking their share of the collective labor, fall into "Irimiash's nationwide spider web" (Irimiash's definition of himself) under the influence of Irimiash's oratory skills and fictitious plans for a bright future.

Revealing the essence of human nature and violence against the backdrop of the collapse of a farm - a social structure - the director identifies his authorial perspective with that of the Doctor's character: the Doctor, who observes and records what is happening in the

village from his window, is actually writing the anatomy of deception.

The camera joins the characters, walking alongside those who are ready to deceive and be deceived, and the film's over-the-shoulder and behind-the-scenes shots draw a sharp line between the author's angle and the camera's angle: the author observing from the window and the camera walking through the illusions. This double perspective encodes both the technical and the emotional point of view of the character-author.

The static shooting method slows down the movement in front of it, seemingly enlarging the scale of individual objects and minimizing the rhythm of even the most visually dynamic scenes. The contrast created by the technical method and the logic of the text becomes the main factor determining the rhythm of the film: while the visually dynamic tango scene has a static quality, the static scenes - the doctor sitting in front of the window, scribbling in his notebook, the frozen state of the girl named Estike, preparing for her death with the cat she killed in her arms - create dynamism. The moment that creates dynamism is the 0.1-second revolution within the static - the girl who cruelly killed the cat tries to meet death with dignity by tidying up her hair with a single movement of her hand, preparing for her own death with dignity. The girl, witnessing the tango, which is apparently the loudest scene in the film, feels this swampy stagnation. In the example of the violent tango on the dance floor, the realization of her violence against the cat leads her to a bottomless pit and leads to suicide. For the girl who is about to die by drinking rat poison, death is the most beautiful, peaceful, innocent way out in this swamp where everyone is deceiving each other. The discrepancy between internal and external signs, one of the main features of carnival aesthetics, manifests itself in the tragedy of this last communal fun before collapse. The last tango of collectivism retains a spirit of mourning for the past, for the experiences that have been shared, and in contrast to the rhythmic tango, it instills sadness. In this case, sadness becomes not only a psychological state but also a state that questions physical existence - you can die of sadness. If you do not join the rhythm of the dance, if you do not repeat this dizzying mantra, if you look as if you are looking out the window, you can die of sadness (just as Estike commits suicide). The closing of the window at the end of the film - the Doctor's nailing pieces of wood to the window to block the view - was a way to escape death.

In general, in Tarr's films, especially in "Damnation" and "Satantango", the dance scenes in bars and dance floors are the opposite of the concept of celebration and fun. The accordion accompaniment, which constantly plays in the background and reinforces the melancholy and nostalgia, cannot be silent along with the rain and wind in the film.

Mihaly Vig's music, heard through an open window, tells of the existence of people somewhere on the other side of the window, in places we cannot see with our eyes, who are also suffering the same pain. That is why music in these films acts as an organic member, not accompanying the plot, but rather entering into the dialogue. This music is what makes the films bearable: the presence of those who share the same sorrow and

fate, even if they are far away, gives comfort to the person (the characters), and this comfort - the presence of fellow sufferers who exist far away - is confirmed by Mihaly Vig's music. In Tarr's films, no force can interrupt the music - the events taking place in parallel with the music on the dance floors and in the bar - crimes, severe interrogations, interrogations, heartbreaks, fights, the most intense arguments - nothing can cover up and bury the music: the music accompanies the most brutal scenes, promoting the logic of coexistence, not the confrontation of good and evil. Based on the idea that boredom has the potential for aesthetic pleasure, French composer Erik Satie, who wrote works in the genre of "furniture music," uncovered the melodies of the monotony of everyday life. Tarr's "boring shots" contain, like these "boring music" melodies, the most ordinary, yet the most complex combinations: a confirmation that the seemingly simple situations in Tarr's filmography stem from the tension and energy behind the ordinary act of human behavior.

In the film "Werckmeister Harmonies", based on the novel "The Melancholy of Resistance" by Laszlo Krasznahorkai, the camera follows the human energy that destroys the harmony - the essence of life.

In the fast-paced, associatively linked film, the elderly art critic and composer Eszter, who dismisses composer Andreas Werckmeister's theory of musical harmony as nonsense, retreats to his room, while the young postal worker Janos acts as an observer at the center of events, witnessing how the depraved masses of people disrupt human harmony. If we proceed from the premise that cinematography, unlike dramaturgy, is "defined by a continuous stream of visual images," [Фельдман, 1959] we can see the full establishment of the power of the laws of cinematography by revealing the associative relationships between the frames of the film.

Tarr illustrates Werckmeister's idea that mathematical precision is the key to restoring harmony in music theory: a measured revolution, a mass of people executing specific orders, disrupts the natural course and sequence of events, creating disharmony. In the film, the mechanized and accelerated steps of the disgruntled and protesting crowd indicate the inhuman nature of the march. At this time, the camera becomes a participant, the angle is chosen in such a way that the viewer, through the camera's eyes, joins the crowd in committing atrocities, turning the hospital upside down, and mercilessly beating the patients - the power of the angle creates an effect of emotional solidarity. The accelerated frame effect returns to normal speed after the crowd leaves the hospital, the tempo slows down. The weakening of a chaotic crowd after committing a crime shows that the path of any chaos towards harmony is slow.

In the film "The Man from London," the event that disrupts the flow of everyday life is when a railway worker near the port witnesses a crime. Maloin, whose main job is to monitor the arrival and departure of trains approaching the port, loses his inner balance after becoming a kind of accomplice to the crime by taking a suitcase full of money belonging to a murdered man. Maloin, who considers himself responsible for solving the crime he was involved in, punishing the criminal,

and returning the money to those who are entitled to it, goes through stages of guilt and purification in a detective plot (the film is based on the screenplay adapted by Tarr and Krasznahorkai from Georges Simenon's novel "The Man from London"). But this purification itself is parallel to the sin, the character who kills the murderer and presents the suitcase of money in his house to the police inspector and awaits his legal arrest is rewarded with money in return. The windows in Maloin's house, closed by his wife, symbolize the impotence and hopelessness of the situation.

Kovacs statement confirming the presence of the observer character in the films allows us to suggest that the view from the window is also the author's perspective: "In the majority of the films made after Almanac of Fall we find a lonely, marginalised protagonist who takes on an outsider's or an observer's position (Karrer in Damnation, the doctor in Satantango, Valuska in Werckmeister Harmonies, Maloin in The Man from London) [Kovacs, 2013]. In Tarr's filmography, windows have an observatory, controlling, and sometimes ruling function: there is always material to watch: "Damnation" depicts the futility of human hopes, "Satantango" depicts the collapse of a village - a community full of deceptions, "The Harmony of the Werckmeister" depicts chaos and the destructive power of the crowd, and "The Man from London" traces the criminal and punishment procedure. Closing these windows, which become a symbol of hopelessness and a visual executioner, closing even the slightest place of hope, symbolizes the characters' escape from any vital initiative and their state of stagnation. Even in "Satantango," the Doctor's not only closing the window at the end, but also nailing it with large planks, is not the end: the physical limitation of the view from the window does not mean that that view disappears. The window to this view will close for the last time in 2011, at the house in the "Turin Horse."

When there's nothing left to look at

The film "The Turin Horse," directed by Bela Tarr and based on Laszlo Krasznahorkai's essay "At the latest in Turin" is the architect's last full-length work.

In "The Turin Horse," the world seen through the window has reached its point of disappearance. The absolute emptiness seen through the window visualizes that there is no longer a landscape to look at. Perhaps this is why the director declared that he would not make a feature film after "The Turin Horse": if there is no point to look at, there is no cinema.

The father with paralyzed right hand, and the daughter, who never tires of the same routine, who undresses and dresses her father with the same energy, cooks potatoes, eats, washes dishes and clothes and sleeps in the same position at the same time, are cut off from their connections with the outside world due to the hurricane. Signs of life fade away one by one: the ever-heard sounds of woodworms cease, the horse refuses to eat, the water in the well dries up, the hearth goes out... And it becomes impossible to leave these places: the devil restores his power - Tarr destroys the world that God created in six days in six days and proves Nietzsche right. The life seen through the windows of the "Turin Horse" establishes the rules of the "Anti-Bible" that the gypsies left for the girl. Realizing that they can

no longer get away, the father and daughter face the end of the world in their hut. At this moment, the shot of the girl looking out the window and the director's authorial angle are reversed - the camera angle and the authorial angle become equal: this shot, which visualizes the camera and the author's face, which are left alone and face to face with the girl in the window, becoming the window, the point of collision between the gazes of the Inside and the Outside, confirms that there is nothing left to look at outside.

The events taking place on the lower floors of the building designed by Bela Tarr (in the early stages of his work) still inspire hope, as the characters fight for a better future and struggle to survive. As you climb to the upper floors, the eye sees further and further, the sense of hopelessness, deception, disappointment and abandonment gradually grows. On the top floor stands the "Turin Horse": there is no way out - absolute hopelessness, absolute existentialism, and this God-forsaken landscape marks the final point of Tarr's work.

Conclusion: An analysis of Bela Tarr's filmography in terms of perspective allows us to conclude that the author's perspective is built precisely in relation to the window in the films. The window is the main means of expression of the author's perspective in Bela Tarr's

full-length feature films. In the first stage of his work, the perspective of looking in through the window is dominant, and in the second stage, the perspective of looking out through the window is dominant.

Bela Tarr's windows: 1. are soundproof; 2. are static; 3. non-breathable. These windows open to various illusions and deceptions. Each window seeks the salvation of man and humanity, new ways of living, and the result proves that the end brought by all these paths is actually a new deception. Endless deceptions continue like a chain reaction - each new generation is doomed to create its own chain of deceptions, weaving each link of the chain with the most complex mechanisms. Bela Tarr opens his windows wide to these most diverse deceptions and he conveys his authorial perspective to the viewer precisely through the view from the window. His authorial perspective also defines his individual style.

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